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Bond behavior between high-strength concrete and steel reinforcement under high cycle fatigue push-in loading

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Abstract

In the last decades, an increasing demand for renewable energy has been stimulating the development of more fatigue resistant wind turbines that can be exposed to millions of load cycles. Bond degradation caused by this high number of load cycles needs to be examined to guarantee the durability and safety of these structures. In this paper, experimental investigations of the bond behavior between high-strength concrete and steel reinforcement under monotonic and high-cycle fatigue loading are presented. In contrast to the pull-out test prevailing in literature, here a push-in compressive loading is applied. Therefore, a modified beam-end test specimen is used. Bond length, concrete strength as well as bar diameter are varied in the presented test program that consisted of 44 beam-end test specimens. The bond strength obtained from the push-in tests for bond length 2.5ds is comparable with the pull-out bond strength values. The results provide the basis for a detailed analysis of the effect of the splitting cracks on the growth of slip in the fatigue tests. Push-through and combined push-through × splitting failure modes have been observed in the experimental program.

1 Introduction

The subject of bond fatigue in reinforced concrete structures has been attracting more attention in recent decades. This is because of the desire to utilize high-strength concrete in building resource-efficient, lightweight, high-strength and durable structures that are exposed to millions of load cycles such as wind turbines. At the same time, sufficiently sound description of the behavior of bond between high-strength concrete and steel reinforcement under fatigue loading is still missing in the literature.

One of the most prominent research efforts in this field is the test program carried out by [1]. A total number of 308 cylindrical pull-out specimens were tested with cyclic loading up to 1 million load cycles and with varied concrete strength up to cubic compression strength of 48 MPa. Other bond repeated loading tests were performed by [2], [3], [4]. Recent studies were performed also in [5], [6], [7]. Investigations focusing on the effect of the transverse tension on the bond behavior under cyclic loading have been reported by [8], [9].

All these studies used the normal-strength concrete matrix with compressive strength of up to 60 MPa. The behavior of bond between high-strength concrete and steel reinforcement under monotonic loading were studied experimentally by many authors e.g. [10], [11], [12], [13]. However, scarce research has been conducted for the case of cyclic loading. Moreover, to the knowledge of the authors no bond strength studies have been conducted elsewhere using a push-in test setup with high-cycle compressive loading. Therefore, it was necessary to characterize the bond between high-strength concrete and steel reinforcement under these loading and setup conditions.

2 Experimental program

2.1 Material properties

2.1.1 Concrete

Two different high-strength concrete classes were used in the tests. According to EuroCode 2 [14], these are the C80/95 and C100/115. However, in this paper they will be referred to as C80 and C120, respectively, depending on a convention among the partners of the collaborative research project

WinConFat focused on the fatigue behavior of wind turbine towers. The properties of the concrete mixtures for the two concrete types are summarized in Table 1. Batches with up to 9 beam-end specimens were casted at once to ensure similar concrete properties. In addition, material tests were performed with each batch to evaluate the development of the compressive strength and the Young's modulus along the period of experimenting. For that purpose, cylinders with a diameter of 150 mm and a height of 300 mm and cubes with an edge length of 150 mm were produced according to [15] and were stored in the laboratory with similar conditions to the beam-end specimens.

The average of the tested cylindrical compressive strength after 28 days was 84.2 MPa and 107 MPa for concrete C80 and C120, respectively. The average of Young's Modulus for concrete C80 was 37827.9 MPa and a value of 50033.6 MPa was obtained for concrete C120.

Table 1 Properties of the used concrete.

Concrete grade	Cement	W/C	Aggregate type	Maximum grain size
C80	CEM I 52,5 R	0,47	50% limestone, 50% quartz	16 mm
C120	CEM I 52,5 R	0,35	quartz	16 mm

2.1.2 Steel

Hot rolled highly ductile deformed bars of the class B500B [16] with yield strength $f_y = 500$ MPa and two different bar diameters of 16 mm and 25 mm were used. The steel bars are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Steel bars used in the tests

2.2 Test set-up

The most common test setup for characterization of the bond behavior is the RILEM pull-out test [17]. In this test, a steel rebar is centrally positioned in a cubic concrete specimen and is exposed to the pull-out load. However, the results obtained from this test lead to overestimated bond strength because of the compressive stresses around the bond zone which originate from reaction forces on the supported surface of the cube. Moreover, the effect of splitting cracks along the bonded zone cannot be studied due to the inevitably large concrete cover. Another, more recent standardized test method for bond strength characterization is provided by the ASTM beam-end test [18]. The placement of supports and loading in this method corresponds better with the stress state in the tensile reinforcement of a RC beam and eliminates the undesired compressive stresses along the bond zone Fig.2.

Fig. 2 Comparison of compressive stresses flow between beam-end test and RILEM test

It is to be mentioned that the bond behavior of rebars under compressive loading in RC elements accompanies an additional resistance mechanism stemming from the concrete cone breakout initiated at the tip of the rebar under compression. The full representation for this combined behaviour is not in the scope of the current test program which is primarily focused on bond behavior under the push-in condition.

For the reasons mentioned above, the beam-end test was chosen for the bond experiments presented here. However, multiple modifications have been conducted on the standard test specimen. First, the dimensions of the specimen were selected to be relative to bar diameter d_s ($L \times W \times H = 20 d_s \times 8 d_s \times 14 d_s$) according to [9] in order to have comparable specimens for the two different diameters Fig. 3 (a). Second, due to the push-in loading that should be applied, a wide recess was introduced to reduce the length of the bar in the loaded end zone, and hence to avoid buckling of the steel bar with. At the same time, the flow of compressive stresses was kept outside of the studied bond zone Fig. 2. Third, to have a realistic bond behavior similar to practical situations and to restrict splitting cracks, two stirrups were used along the bonded length for the tests with $2.5 d_s$ bond length and four were used for tests with bond length of $5 d_s$. Finally, three longitudinal bars were arranged on each side of the specimen to restrict the transversal cracks emerging due to the introduced recess Fig. 3 (b).

Two LVDTs (Linear variable differential transformers) were used to record the slip on the loaded and unloaded ends of the steel bar. In addition, one LVDT was mounted on the specimen surface over the bond zone to record the width of the longitudinal crack (splitting crack) along the bond and another one was mounted on the side of the specimen to record the width of the transversal crack Fig. 3 (b).

Fig. 3 a) Sketch of the modified beam-end specimen with the dimensions and reinforcement details; b) the setup of the 4 LVDTs with cracks positions

2.3 Loading scenarios

For the monotonic tests, a displacement-controlled loading with a rate of 1.0 mm/min was applied until reaching a predefined displacement at the unloaded end (8 to 12 mm). The value of the ultimate push-in load F_u obtained from the monotonic test was then used to define the limit values for the fatigue tests which were force-controlled. The cyclic tests were applied with a constant lower and upper load levels until fatigue failure. Loading frequency of 5Hz or 10Hz was used with upper load levels ranging between $S_{\max} = 0.7$ and $S_{\max} = 0.85$ and lower load levels between $S_{\min} = 0.2$ and $S_{\min} = 0.4$. If 10 million cycles were reached without having a fatigue failure, the specimen was loaded monotonically until failure.

3 Experimental results and discussion

3.1 Monotonic tests

In total, 29 monotonic tests were conducted in this test program. A summary of the results of these tests with statistical evaluation is presented in Table. 3. The observed failure mode for all monotonic tests can be classified as a push-through \times splitting failure mode.

The average of the ultimate push-in force for each set of tests is provided in addition to the respective bond strength supposing a constant stress distribution along the bond zone. The coefficient of variation (CoV) demonstrates the scattering of the ultimate force values. By comparing the CoV for C80 tests with a diameter of 16 mm and bond of 2.5 ds with the bond length 5 ds, it is to be noticed that the scatter of results is larger for shorter bond lengths from the same bar diameter. Also, the results of the C80 concrete show larger scatter in comparison with the values of the concrete C120.

The emergence of the splitting crack is vital for the interpretation of the failure process as it signifies the transition from a bond resistance mechanism controlled by the adhesion, mechanical friction and interlocking between steel ribs and concrete to a more complex tri-axial mechanism affected by the thickness of the concrete cover and the hoop stresses evolving around the bond zone. The force F_{crack} corresponding to the initialization of the splitting crack is provided in Table. 3 in addition to the ratio F_{crack}/F_u . The slip measured at the unloaded end when the ultimate force F_u is reached is also provided and denoted as $w(F_u)$.

Table 3 Results and statistical evaluation of the monotonic tests (LS1).

Tests	Concrete	ds [mm]	Lb	Num. tests	F_u [kN]	τ_u [MPa]	CoV [%]	F_{crack} [kN]	F_{crack}/F_u	$w(F_u)$ [mm]
T1 to T9	C80	16	2.5 ds	9	58.69	29.19	11.0	52.94	0.90	0.215
T10 to T15		16	5 ds	6	95.22	23.68	6.7	76.58	0.80	0.314
T16 to T19		25	2.5 ds	4	116.24	25.82	8.6	95.39	0.82	0.542
T28 to T33	C120	16	2.5 ds	6	72.30	35.96	5.2	67.18	0.93	0.202
T34 to T37		25	2.5 ds	4	167.58	34.14	7.2	158.95	0.95	0.157

The load-displacement curves measured at the loaded and unloaded ends are plotted in Figs. 4(a-c) for five different tests including all the investigated parameter combinations. The curves show a good match between the loaded and unloaded end response curves. Therefore, our assumption of a constant stress distribution in bond zone is valid and the measurements of the unloaded end will be adapted for all subsequent graphs in the paper. It is to be mentioned that despite the multiple precautions to avoid bar buckling in the force introduction zone, a small bending has occurred in some tests causing negative LVDT values at the pre-peak branch of the loaded end curves as shown in Fig. 4(a).

The push-in curves of the unloaded end for all monotonic tests are provided in Figs. 4(d-f). The development of the splitting cracks is illustrated in terms of slip versus crack width curves, plotted together with the corresponding push-in curves up to the slip level of 2 mm Figs. 4(g-i). These diagrams demonstrate the degradation of bond stiffness after the initiation of the splitting crack. This state is marked by an unfilled circle corresponding to the force F_{crack} . The force continues increasing with the reduced bond stiffness up to the ultimate value F_u , followed by the deterioration of the bond resistance with a rapid growth of the splitting crack opening until the termination of the experiment.

According to the FIB Model Code 2010[19], the bond strength of normal-strength concrete with pull-out failure can be calculated as a function of the concrete compressive strength as

$$\tau_u = 2.5 \cdot \sqrt{f_{cm, cyl}} \quad (1)$$

where $f_{cm, cyl}$ is the cylindrical compressive strength of concrete. Another, more complex expression for $\tau_{u, split}$ was also given in [19], which takes the confining conditions and the effect of concrete cover into account. For the case of high-strength concrete a formula was proposed in [20] as

$$\tau_u = 0.45 \cdot f_{cm, cyl} \quad (2)$$

In Fig. 5(a), each measured value of bond strength is plotted against the corresponding cylindrical concrete strength obtained from the accompanying material tests. For comparison, the graphs from

Model Code 2010 and [20] are also displayed. The results show that the formulas in the Model Code underestimate the bond strength values. For the constraining level and the configuration that we used in this test campaign, a ratio of 0.32 is obtained between the bond strength and the cylindrical concrete strength i.e. $\tau_u = 0.32 \cdot f_{cm, cyl}$. The bond strength values normalized w.r.t. the concrete strength are shown in Fig. 5(b). The effect of rebar diameter on the bond strength is represented in Fig. 5(c). The values suggest that larger bar diameters lead to smaller effective bond strengths.

Fig. 4 Results of the monotonic tests; a-c) push-in curves for loaded and unloaded ends; d-f) push-in curves on the unloaded end for all monotonic tests; g-i) development of splitting cracks.

3.2 Fatigue tests

The total number of obtained cycles for each fatigue test is summarized in Table 3 together with the observed failure modes and upper and lower loading levels S_{max} and S_{min} . The tests T26 and T27 were terminated after achieving more than 10 million cycles without failure. In contrast to the push-through \times splitting failure mode, a pure push-through mode means that no splitting crack developed in the respective specimen. A pure splitting failure is not relevant here as this type of failure implies that no confining reinforcement were used. However, in our case two stirrups were used in the bond zone of every test to restrict the growth of the splitting cracks as mentioned earlier Fig. 3.

Fig. 5 Comparisons for bond strength values obtained in the monotonic tests; a) effect of the concrete grade on the bond strength; b) normalized bond strength with respect to the concrete compressive strength; c) effect of the rebar diameter on the bond strength

Table 3 Summary of the fatigue tests (Lb = 2.5 ds).

Tests	Concrete	ds [mm]	S_{max}	S_{min}	Cycles Number	Failure mode
T20 / T21	C80	16	0.8	0.4	20,388/8,345	push-through × splitting
T22 / T23		16	0.75	0.4	993 / 21,525	push-through × splitting
T24 / T25		16	0.7	0.4	7,254 / 23,033	push-through × splitting
T26 / T27		25	0.75	0.4	10,879,726* / 12,459,245*	no fatigue failure
T38/T39/T40	C120	16	0.75	0.2	1,185,480 / 235 / 3,147	push-through
T41/T42/T43		16	0.85	0.2	2,110 / 1,521,020 / 39,435	push-through × splitting
T44		16	0.85	0.2	245	push-through

The fatigue creep curves representing the growing push-in slip during the cyclic loading process for one test for each combination of varied parameters are illustrated in Figs. 6(a, b, d, e, g) with the corresponding splitting crack development. An accelerated slip growth is observed for cycles following the initialization of the splitting crack. The diagrams demonstrate that the higher the upper loading limit S_{max} , the earlier the splitting crack appears. Moreover, comparing the results of the concrete C120 and the concrete C80 one can conclude that the crack emerged much earlier in the C80 results for the same upper load levels. This explains the pure push-through failure of the C120 tests with an upper load limit $S_{max} = 0.75$ as in the case of Fig. 6(a) where no splitting crack has been detected.

Figs. 6(c, h) compare the fatigue lifetimes obtained from all cyclic tests with the Wöhler curves available in the literature. The scatter of the results is in the usual range observed in bond fatigue experiments. Taking into consideration the difference between our lower load level S_{min} and the lower load level of the presented Wöhler curves, these curves proposed in [1] show some overestimation of the fatigue lifetime for the tests of the concrete C80, and on the other hand, it relatively underestimates the lifetimes obtained from concrete C120.

4 Conclusions

The presented campaign of beam-end tests under push-in loading is a part of a larger campaign that includes C120, C80 and C40 concrete classes aimed at the characterization of the bond behavior between steel and concrete under high-cycle fatigue loading. Results for monotonic and fatigue tests conducted so far are introduced and discussed. As a result, following conclusions can be derived:

- The formulas for the calculation of bond strength suggested in the FIB Model Code 2010 underestimate the actual bond strength between high-strength concrete and the deformed steel rebars subjected to push-in loading. According to the configuration and confining

conditions used in this test campaign, the formula $\tau_u = 0.32 \cdot f_{cm, cyl}$ between bond strength and cylindrical concrete strength was obtained.

- The failure mode observed in the conducted beam-end tests was a combined push-through \times splitting failure in all monotonic tests and in most of the fatigue tests. However, some fatigue tests failed with a pure push-through failure without splitting cracks.
- Splitting cracks have a direct impact on the bond fatigue behavior and they accelerate the bond fatigue failure. This effect increases with the increase of the subcritical load level.

Fig. 6 Bond behavior under fatigue loading; a-b) fatigue creep curve with corresponding crack development c) comparison of the results for C120 with Wöhler curves; d-f) fatigue creep curves with corresponding crack opening evolutions g) fatigue creep curve with corresponding crack opening for C80 and diameter $ds = 25\text{mm}$ with $S_{max} = 0.75$; h) comparison of C80 results with Wöhler curves

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